

Market Analysis of a Data Platform in the European Data Ecosystem

Gabriel G. Castane¹, Alejandro Martinez², Qusai Ramadan³, Zaneta Gkika⁴,
Mpempis Panagiotis⁴, and Eduardo Vyhmeister¹(✉)

¹ Insight Centre of Data Analytics, University College Cork, Cork, Ireland
eduardo.vyhmeister@insight-centre.org

² Instituto Tecnológico de Informatica (ITI), Valencia, Spain

³ University of Koblenz, Koblenz, Germany

⁴ OTE Group of Companies (HTO), Athens, Greece

Abstract. In the era of data analytics, industries can use data to enhance market analyses and seek better opportunities for current, or new, business opportunities. Furthermore, companies can consider their data as an intangible asset, allowing expansion, by a proper market analysis, and economic opportunities through data monetization. These strategies define the use of data for indirect and direct purposes. Despite the idea of adopting data monetization practices, a considerable gap exists between expectations and reality. For example, the definition of strategies, methods, and analyses to perform data valuation. This gap necessitates a comprehensive exploration considering the different nuisances of data monetization. To achieve a broader understanding of the data monetization landscape, a market evaluation, through an exploration of the market environment and the stakeholders involved, is necessary. The present work contributes to this understanding by facilitating a market analysis for data valuation within the European community. This analysis aims to shed light on critical aspects influencing the valuation of data in the European context, offering insights into the market dynamics, emerging trends, and the evolving landscape of data monetization strategies within this region.

Keywords: Market analysis · Data Monetization · Data market

1 Introduction

The growth in global data production is evident. It increased from 33 zettabytes in 2018 to a projected 175 zettabytes by 2025. Digital data are exchanged as products or services which results in increasing the value of the data marketplaces. In 2021, the value of the Europe data market was 63.8 billion, a 4.9% increase with respect to the observed in 2020. However, it is expected that there will be a peak in the growth by 2030 with a 6.8% increase between 2025 to 2030 (translated up to 125 billion) [1].

This increase in data production and trading poses a set of challenging positions for the European Union (EU) to assert its global leadership in the scope creating opportunities on paradigms such as data storage, processing, heterogeneity or benefits on their exploitation.

Currently, the main functionalities of data processing and analytical functions, approximately 80%, are concentrated within centralized data centres, while the remaining 20% is distributed across smart connected entities, encompassing vehicular platforms, domestic appliances, manufacturing automation, and proximal user-centric computing facilities—referred to as ‘edge computing’ [2]. This prospective realignment not only underscores economic and sustainable advantages but also engenders novel prospects for enterprises to devise tools facilitating data producers in augmenting their dominion over proprietary data.

For enterprises to actively obtain benefits from data, a thorough understanding of the market and the value of their digital assets in the current market is needed. Thus, conducting market analysis to seize economic opportunities through data monetization is key to define strategies for data monetization (e.g. strategic could pursuit the utilization of consumer data for both indirect and direct benefits). Despite the prevalent idea of adopting data monetization practices, a research gap exists, specifically concerning the factors influencing data valuation. This gap necessitates a comprehensive exploration considering the intricacies involved in decision-making processes within the data monetization domain.

To achieve a broader understanding of the landscape of data monetization, an exploration of the market environment and the stakeholders involved becomes imperative. This analysis should aim to shed light on critical aspects influencing the valuation of data in the European context, offering insights into the market dynamics, emerging trends, and the evolving landscape of data monetization strategies within this region.

The purpose of this work (market analysis) is to inform the exploitation strategy and development of the business plan by investigating the current state of the European data marketplace sector and its needs for data monetization. More specifically, the idea is to evaluate the market analysis for a Data Platform in the European Data Ecosystem contained within an ongoing case study. The case study involves the European Project DATAMITE, which combines expertise from industry and academia in the. Readers are encouraged to read more about this project that focuses on the monetization of data within Europe [3].

Firstly, in Sect. 2, we will start with the market analysis evaluating the size, trends, and projected growth of different identified indicators (based on different scenarios). Following this, in Sect. 3, the target audience will be examined, the technology implementation in the European data platforms. Section 4 will cover, the current needs of data platforms from a European implementation point of view. Section 5 covers the technology maturity of Europe for the implementation of data platforms. Section 6 describes the results of a deeper analysis of the market by providing the Barriers and Opportunities from a SWOT analysis. Finally, in Sect. 7, the most important remarks of this work will be given as a conclusion.

2 Market Analysis for Data Monetization – Size and Trends

2.1 Size, Trends and Projected Growth

To conduct a rigorous analysis of data monetization, it is imperative to delineate a precise market segment that encapsulates this specific domain. The focus of this study is on data monetization within the European Information Technology (IT) market, and as such, the ensuing analyses are tailored to this segment.

Projections regarding the data market were obtained from Eurostat [4], where the yearly % GDP growth rate of the EU from 2011 to 2022 was considered. In the year 2020, the European Union experienced a contraction of 5.6% in its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The COVID-19 crisis triggered the most substantial economic downturn in the history of the European Union, surpassing the impact of the 2007–2008 financial crisis, which saw a 4.3% contraction. Notably, the distinguishing factor in terms of GDP fluctuation between these two crises lies in their subsequent recoveries. While it took several years to overcome the recession of 2007–2008, the EU's GDP rebounded beyond pre-pandemic levels within a single year after the conclusion of lockdowns. Despite the severity of the impact, the European Union demonstrated remarkable resilience.

The third iteration of EDM research highlights the resilience and adaptability of the European IT market during the challenging period of 2020–2021. According to IDC's projections [1], the market value surged from 584 billion euros in 2020 to 624 billion euros in 2021, aligning with the EU's percentual GDP growth. A further 3% increase is anticipated in 2022. Despite the lingering impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic into 2021, the outlook for IT investments remained steadfast, with many European enterprises actively pursuing technology advancements for innovation and adaptation to the evolving landscape, solidifying the digital-first paradigm.

Following the crisis outbreak, the final policy conclusion of the second edition of the EDM monitoring tool included an analysis of the crisis impact. As per [1], predictions in May 2020 foresaw a 7.1% decrease in the European Data Market to 54 billion euros and a 5.5% fall in the Data Economy to 307 billion euros from the previous prediction of 325 billion euros in 2019. Despite the negative impact of COVID-19 on the European economy, it was anticipated that growth would occur in the following years.

The labour market, a lagging indicator reflecting macroeconomic conditions, showed a significant decrease in the active workforce during the COVID-19 pandemic until the first quarter of 2021 [5]. However, the number of ICT specialists not only withstood the uncertainties but also significantly accelerated its growth during this period. The growth of employed ICT specialists accelerated from 3.7% in 2018–2019 to 7.2% in 2019–2020 and 6% in 2020–2021 [6]. Considering factors such as increased efforts in Artificial Intelligence (AI) system development, the ICT sector, especially the data economy, is believed to be experiencing a secular tailwind.

2.2 Indicators to Monitor Data Markets

There are 6 indicators to monitor the European Data Market, according to [1]:

- **Data Professionals:** Individuals responsible for data collection, storage, administration, analysis, interpretation, and visualization, encompassing both technical experts and business professionals.

- **Data Professionals Skills Gap:** Refers to the potential disparity between the demand and supply of data-related skills in Europe.
- **Data Companies:** Divided into data suppliers, creating and distributing digital data-related products, and data users, organizations using digital data to enhance business operations.
- **Data Suppliers' Revenues:** Collective worth of data-related products and services produced by EU companies specializing in data supply.
- **Value of the Data Market:** Quantifies the worth of marketplaces where digital data is traded as products or services, resulting from refined raw data.
- **Value of the Data Economy:** Gauges the comprehensive effects of the data market on the overall economy, encompassing the worth of marketplaces where digital data is traded as products or services, stemming from refined raw data.

The latest European Data Market (EDM) study introduces three scenarios for the European Data Economy: (1) Baseline Scenario, (2) High Growth Scenario, and (3) Challenge Scenario.

Baseline Scenario: Assumes that current growth trends will persist, and existing framework conditions will evolve accordingly. Anticipated outcomes include a robust increase in data innovation, limited consolidation of power among major data holders, the presence of a data governance system protecting individual data rights, and a reasonably widespread distribution of benefits from data innovation throughout society.

High Growth Scenario: Envision a more rapid expansion of the data market due to increasingly favourable framework conditions. The scenario is characterized by an accelerated pace of data innovation and digital transformation. It anticipates data sharing facilitated by a globally acknowledged data governance framework.

Challenge Scenario: The data market experiences a slower growth rate compared to the baseline scenario due to less advantageous framework conditions and less favourable macroeconomic circumstances.

Forecasts for the six indicators will be provided for both 2025 and 2030 in each of these scenarios to offer insights into potential future trajectories. It is worth mentioning that the calculated rate for the rest of the report is the Compound Annual Growth Rate and its formula is (Where t is in years):

$$CAGR(\%) = \left(\frac{\text{endingvalue}}{\text{startingvalue}} \right)^{\frac{1}{t}} - 1$$

The data professional's analysis found 6.5 million professionals in Europe in 2020, growing to 6.8 million in 2021 (5.4% growth) [4]. In the baseline scenario, it projects 8 million professionals in 2025 and 9.6 million in 2030 (3.4% growth). The high-growth scenario estimates 8 million professionals in 2025 and 11 million in 2030 (7% growth). The less favourable challenge scenario predicts an increase from 8 to 8.7 million professionals between 2025 and 2030 (1.5% growth).

When analyzing the data professional's skills gap indicator, different trends were observed. Between 2020 and 2021, there was a 64.3% increase, rising from 206 thousand to 338 thousand. In the baseline scenario, predictions indicate that it will reach 451 thousand by 2025 and 500 thousand by 2030, with a growth rate of 2.1%. Under the

high-growth scenario, the numbers were projected to be 451 thousand in 2025 and 1.062 million in 2030, reflecting an 18.7% growth rate. The least favorable scenario predicts a 14% decrease, from 451 thousand in 2025 to 211 thousand in 2030.

Figure 1 illustrates the trend in data companies, distinguishing between data suppliers and data users. Data suppliers experienced a 5.8% growth from 176,000 companies in 2020 to 185,000 in 2021. Data users, on the other hand, grew by 1.9%, reaching 553,000 organizations by 2021. In the baseline scenario, data suppliers are predicted to be 252,000 in 2025 and 295,000 in 2030, with a growth rate of 3.1%. Data users are expected to exhibit a higher rate of 7.2%, reaching 633,000 in 2025 and 898,000 in 2030. Under the high-growth scenario, data suppliers are projected to be 252,000 in 2025 and 311,000 in 2030, with a growth rate of 4.4%. Data users are anticipated to nearly triple, with numbers reaching 633,000 in 2025 and 1.086 million in 2030, at a rate of 11.4%. In the challenge scenario, data suppliers are expected to decline by 8.3%, from 252,000 to 163,000. Data users are predicted to grow by 3.5%, going from 633,000 to 753,000 organizations in 2025 and 2030, respectively.

Analyzing the fourth indicator, depicting data suppliers' revenues, a growth of 2.9% was observed between the economic years 2020 and 2021, increasing from 71 to 73 billion euros. In the baseline scenario, the projected value for 2025 is 104 billion euros, with a growth rate of 3.4%, reaching 123 billion euros by 2030. Under the high-growth scenario, revenues are expected to be 104 billion euros in 2025 and 152 billion euros in 2030, with a growth rate of 7.9%. In the challenging scenario, a modest growth rate of 0.9% is anticipated, going from 104 billion in 2025 to 108 billion euros in 2030.

Fig. 1. The data suppliers and data users trend for the three scenarios.

In analyzing the fifth indicator, depicting the value of data marketplaces in Europe, a growth of 4.9% was observed between 2020 and 2021, increasing from 61 to 64 billion euros. In the baseline scenario, the projected value for the data market is 90 billion euros in 2025 and 106 billion euros in 2030, with a growth rate of 3.2%. Under the high-growth scenario, the values are 90 billion euros in 2025 and 125 billion euros in 2030, with a growth rate of 6.8%. In the challenging scenario, the value of the data market is expected

to follow the same rate as data suppliers' revenue in that scenario, standing at 90 billion euros in 2025 and 94 billion euros in 2030.

In examining the last indicator, which assesses the impact of the data market on the overall economy, there was a growth of 4.9% between 2020 and 2021, increasing from 422 billion to 443 billion euros. Under the baseline scenario, the value of the data economy (indicator 6) is projected to grow at a rate of 5.4%, reaching 604 billion euros in 2025 and contributing 787 billion euros to the entire economy by 2030. In the high-growth scenario, the value is expected to be 604 billion euros in 2025, with a growth rate of 9.6%, resulting in a value of 955 billion euros in 2030. In the challenging scenario, the value of the data economy stands at 604 billion euros in 2025 and 687 billion euros in 2030, with a growth rate of 2.6%.

In each indicator, the baseline scenario shows an increase in associated values, while the high-growth scenario exhibits even greater growth rates between the two years. The challenge scenario, although lower than the baseline, still sees increases in most indicators, with two exceptions showing negative rates for indicators 2 and 3.

The past years have seen a significant rise in the values of the six indicators, with forecasts predicting further increases in the next seven years. The potential decrease in the number of data suppliers in the challenge scenario by 2030 is a concern. However, the close alignment between the baseline and high-growth scenarios is encouraging, hinting at the likelihood of maintaining the observed growth rate.

3 Market Analysis Data Monetization – Customers and Target Audience

3.1 Stakeholders

In this section, we analyze potential organizations for data monetization across different categories: (1) Core Organizations, (2) Supporting Organizations, (3) Distribution Channels, (4) Regulatory and Policy Entities, and (5) Research and Development. Figure 2 illustrates organizations/stakeholders in these categories.

For the first Category (**Core Organizations**) the stakeholders include (i) Data Providers - Collect and generate data from various sources, supplying it to other entities. (ii) Data Analytics companies - Specialize in analyzing data for valuable insights, utilizing statistical analysis, machine learning, and data visualization. (iii) Data Science Labs – These are research-oriented organizations focused on developing advanced data analysis techniques and models. (iv) Government Agencies - collect and manage diverse data for regulatory and policy purposes, and (v) Non-profit organizations - Use data for social good, research, or advocacy, focusing on issues like public health, education, environmental conservation, or humanitarian efforts.

For the second category, **Supporting Organizations**, several key stakeholders contribute to data monetization. These include: (i) Data Integration Service Providers – They specialize in integrating data from diverse sources to create unified datasets for analysis. (ii) Data Visualization Studios - They are also part of this category, crafting visual representations (e.g. charts and graphs) for better comprehension of complex information. (iii) Data Governance Consultants – These stakeholders aid organizations in establishing policies and procedures for effective data management, ensuring quality, security,

compliance, and adherence to standards. (iv) Data Storage and Infrastructure Providers - They offer the necessary hardware and software infrastructure for data storage, processing, and management, including data centres, cloud services, and storage solutions. (v) Data Security Firms – These stakeholders play a crucial role by specializing in safeguarding data from unauthorized access, breaches, and cyberattacks. Their solutions, such as encryption and access control, contribute to protecting sensitive information in the data monetization ecosystem.

Fig. 2. Stakeholders and organizations for the different categories.

In the **Distribution Channels** category, organizations play distinct roles, including (i) Data Marketplaces - Marketplaces serve as platforms where data providers offer their data for sale or exchange, and data consumers can acquire data through licensing agreements or subscriptions. (ii) Data as a Service Providers (DaaS) - DaaS providers offer data-related services on a subscription basis, providing access to specific datasets and performing functions like data cleansing and enrichment. (iii) Data Publishers - Create and distribute datasets, reports, or publications derived from data analysis, presenting information in a structured and usable format. (iv) Data Aggregators - collect data from diverse sources, compiling it into comprehensive datasets or databases that can be used in different applications and domains.

In the **Regulatory and Policy Entities** category, the organizations include (i) Data Protection Agencies - oversee and enforce data privacy and protection regulations, ensuring organizations handle personal data in compliance with legal requirements. (ii) Data Ethics Committees - guide ethical considerations related to data collection, usage,

and sharing, assisting organizations in making responsible and ethical data decisions. (iii) Standards Bodies – focus on developing and maintaining standards and protocols, ensuring interoperability, consistency, and quality in data exchange and management.

Finally, the **Research and Development** is composed of (i) Data Science Research Institutions - dedicated to advancing the field through research, experimentation, and innovation. They often collaborate with academia and industry to push the boundaries of data science. (ii) Innovation Hubs – They foster creativity and collaboration in the ecosystem, providing resources and support for entrepreneurs, startups, and innovators. (iii) Technology Providers – They participate as software and technologies facilitators. The technologies can be diverse including, but not limited to, data collection, analysis, and management.

3.2 Technology Implementation in the European Sector

In this section, we will showcase various technologies that are required by data platforms in Europe. These requirements include: (1) **GDPR**: According to [7], strict adherence to GDPR requires obtaining user consent through clear and concise requests, using easily understandable language that is distinguishable from other information such as terms and conditions. It is imperative to specify the intended use of personal data and provide contact details for the organization. (2) **Security and Robustness**: In data platform security, robust measures such as encryption, access controls, and auditing, as recommended by [8], are crucial for protecting sensitive information. Techniques like encryption, data erasure, masking, and data resiliency contribute to safeguarding data integrity. (3) **Cross-border frameworks**: Cross-border data transfer, especially in the European Economic Area (EEA), faces complexities due to strict rules. Platforms need to support secure transfers while complying with GDPR restrictions, as outlined in [9]. Solutions include data mapping, encryption, and anonymisation. **Sovereignty**: Data localization and sovereignty are key considerations. Compliance with residency requirements involves storing data within national borders, with options like on-premises storage, cloud storage, data transfer, and data processing. **Quality**: Quality of data is ensured through observability, involving real-time monitoring and measurement across key dimensions. Core capabilities include automated monitoring, intelligent alerts, and end-to-end lineage to improve time-to-detection and resolution of data issues. **Ethics and Trustworthy AI**: Ethics and ethical AI are essential, and soon legal requirements for AI assets. These can be translated into transparent and fair data hosting, avoiding discrimination. Internal measurement of metrics ensures compliance with desired ethical thresholds. **Portability and Interoperability**: Data portability and interoperability are critical. Platforms should facilitate data transfer as per GDPR, and promote interoperability through standard formats and protocols like JSON, XML, CSV, RESTful APIs, and harvesters. Data serialization, catalogues, and metadata are essential for achieving interoperability.

4 Data Platforms – Current Needs

In today's data-driven world, the role of data platforms in various industries has become increasingly vital. Organizations across the globe are recognizing the importance of harnessing data to gain insights, make informed decisions, and stay competitive. This section delves into the current needs for a data platform that facilitates the process of data monetization. Thus, this analysis is made based on an approach of a stakeholder that offers services (in the form of data) obtaining benefits through it. The following list is based on analyses performed on the use case mentioned above.

Real-time Data Analysis: Necessity for efficient real-time processing and analysis of structured and unstructured data from diverse sources. Vital for swift decision-making and enhanced customer experiences, particularly in dynamic industries.

Scalability and Flexibility: Essential features include scalability to accommodate growing data volumes and flexibility to integrate new data sources and technologies.

Data Security and Compliance: Robust security measures, including encryption and access controls, to address data breaches and comply with regulations (e.g. GDPR).

AI and Machine Learning Integration: Support for AI and ML initiatives, providing the required infrastructure and capabilities for training and deploying models.

Cross-Channel Data Integration: capability to integrate data from various channels for a comprehensive view of operations and customer behavior.

Hybrid and Multi-Cloud Compatibility: Versatility to manage data seamlessly across different cloud providers, ensuring interoperability and data portability.

Data Monetization: Enablement of secure data sharing and analytics for organizations to explore opportunities for selling data and creating data-driven products.

Data Governance: inclusion of features for data governance, allowing organizations to set policies, track data lineage, and adhere to regulatory requirements.

Data Residency and Sovereignty: Data sovereignty concerns are growing, with certain countries imposing data residency requirements, mandating that data must be stored within their borders. Data platforms must provide options for data residency while ensuring data accessibility and global compliance.

Disaster Recovery and Business Continuity: In an era of digital disruptions, having a robust data platform for data backup, disaster recovery, and business continuity is imperative. The platform should ensure data is protected and recoverable in case of unexpected incidents.

Improved Customer Experiences: Central role in aggregating and analyzing customer data to personalize products and services.

Operational Efficiency: Data platforms are increasingly being used to optimize internal processes. Businesses can gain insights into resource allocation, inventory management, and supply chain optimization. Operational efficiency can be improved by leveraging data-driven insights.

Bureaucratic Hurdles: In some regions, navigating administrative and bureaucratic requirements related to data management, reporting, and compliance can be a barrier to implementing data platforms. Streamlining these processes is essential for smooth platform deployment.

Data Collaboration: Collaborative data sharing and analysis with partners and third parties can be a driving factor in certain industries. Data platforms should facilitate secure data exchanges and offer options for collaboration in a trusted environment.

Language and Cultural Diversity: In a globalized world, organizations must deal with language and cultural diversity when managing data. Data platforms should be capable of accommodating various languages and cultural nuances, especially in applications that involve user-generated content and customer interactions.

The Future of Data Platforms: As the data landscape continues to evolve, the needs for data platforms will evolve as well. Emerging technologies like 5G, edge computing, and quantum computing will present new opportunities and challenges. Organizations must remain agile and adapt their data platforms to harness the potential of these technologies.

5 Data Platforms – Technology Maturity in the European Sector

The technology maturity influences decisions on data management and analytics strategies. Europe today is leading the development and adoption of emerging technologies in data platforms. For example, the UK, Germany, and France offer startups and research institutions driving advances in artificial intelligence and data analytics. Although not realized in real-world scenarios, these technologies, approaches, and contributions have the potential to revolutionize data platforms. In the following, we describe them:

Open Source and Collaborative Communities: The open-source community contributes to the development of data platform technology. For example, projects such as Apache Hadoop, Apache Spark, and various NoSQL databases are well-known among European organizations. The open-source culture provides a channel for collaboration and knowledge sharing, which enhances the accessibility to advanced data technologies in the European market.

Cloud Adoption and Data Sovereignty: The use of data platforms from cloud providers such as AWS, Azure, and others is growing significantly in Europe. The reason for this is that these providers provide local data centres that comply with data privacy regulations and offer data sovereignty solutions. This enables organizations in Europe to benefit from cloud solutions that are cost-effective and address data sovereignty concerns.

Data Privacy and Security Regulations: There is a growing demand for technologies with strong security and compliance features. This is due to strict data privacy laws in Europe. Therefore, Europe today is witnessing the development of many platforms that incorporate privacy-enhanced technology data sovereignty solutions while supporting data analytics.

AI and Machine Learning Integration: The investment of the European market in AI-based applications like data analytics and automation is witnessing projected growth in comparison with the last ten years. AI-based applications becoming a reliable part of today's data platforms, which enables several services such as advanced data processing and analysis.

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies: BCT (Blockchain technology) provides the chance to enhance efficiency, transparency, and traceability through its ability to enable immutable data records and create traceable transaction histories. In

Europe, BCT is being employed across various industries, including sectors such as insurance, healthcare, and energy.

Industry-Specific Solutions and Customization: European industries vary in data management and analytics needs. For example, in the healthcare domain, organizations have different data analytic needs compared to the needs in the automotive manufacturing domain. This results in the need for industry-specific data platforms that meet sector-specific requirements.

Collaborative Ecosystems for Innovation: European countries are looking for a more collaborative culture between different sectors. Therefore, some platforms aim to bring startups, academia, and industry together in one ecosystem. This will help organizations to share knowledge and also stay up-to-date concerning advancements in the data space.

6 Data Platforms – Opportunities and Barriers

Based on the previous discussion, and analyses performed on the current state of the art of the data market in Europe, the following opportunities and barriers can be defined for data monetization through a data platform in the European Data Ecosystem.

6.1 Opportunities

The implementation of a data platform in the European data ecosystem can create several opportunities for organizations, regardless of the industrial sector. The big diversity of industries offers multiple opportunities while implementing a data platform, such as:

Revenue Generation: By monetizing their data, companies can create new streams of revenue. One stream of revenue comes from selling data to third parties for different purposes such as market analysis.

Improved Decision-Making: Data monetization enables collecting accurate insights and expectations about the business and market status. Specifically, by analyzing the data, companies can make more informed decisions and optimize their costs and services.

Enhanced Customer Experience: A better understanding of the customers' needs requires monetizing data between companies in one specific sector or many sectors. For example, access to a database that provides information about customers from different demographics can help a specific business personalize its advertisements, enhance its services, and improve customer experience.

Industry Leadership: With the effective use of data monetization strategies within a data ecosystem, companies can position themselves as industry pioneers. Specifically, data monetization allows companies to stay ahead of their competitors, innovate, and drive growth in their industries.

Collaboration and Partnerships: Data monetization creates opportunities for collaboration and partnerships. Companies can form strategic alliances with other organizations, leveraging their data assets creating mutual benefits and unlocking new value.

Introducing the Digital Transformation: by collecting, analyzing and processing huge amounts of raw data, each organization can identify trends and uncover new insights. This leads to innovation and to data-driven decision-making. Therefore, it contributes to the overall digital transformation of businesses across various sectors.

Ecosystem collaboration: Successful data monetization involves collaborative ecosystems where organizations form partnerships to exchange data and create synergies. Extending beyond traditional industry boundaries, these ecosystems include diverse players such as individuals, organizations, or systems. An effective external data monetization strategy requires both a data-consuming party and a data-providing party.

Integration of advanced technologies and Customer-centric approach: Zaki et al. [10] propose a Data-Driven Business Model (DDBM) that utilizes advanced technologies, including artificial intelligence, to help organizations identify patterns in large datasets to understand and meet customer needs, which can result in more personalized services, and experiences.

6.2 Barriers

The European Data Ecosystem is a thriving landscape characterized by a rich diversity of organizations from the previous 6 categories. Although the potential to leverage data into the ecosystem is enormous, organizations seeking to implement data platforms often face various barriers, which prevent companies and research institutions from reaching their goals.

Regulatory Complexities: Organizational complexities: Due to the dynamic nature of data and the ambiguity of the legal guidelines [12], organizations face difficulties in correctly implementing data rights and ownership, which result in non-compliance with the laws and legal disputes. Therefore, addressing these issues is of high importance to a secure data environment. For example, cross-border data transfers require organizations to comply with different regulations across multiple countries, which increases complexity. For this, we believe that organizations must implement robust data privacy management in all their system development life cycle including coding, and auditing capabilities.

Economic and Financial Barriers: Due to small budgets and limited funding resources, small organizations in Europe face challenges in covering the costs of implementing and maintaining data ecosystems. As a result, small organizations lose competitive advantages because they cannot align the economic incentives to share data. Other high costs arise from the absence of strong legal and ethical frameworks, and privacy concerns, which require the employment of highly paid experts and consultants.

Technical Obstacles: Technical challenges pose significant barriers to implementing data platforms in the European Data Ecosystem. Some of these challenges are also discussed in [12] described as challenges and they can involve:

- (1) *Ensuring Data security and Sovereignty.* Data platforms in the European Data Ecosystem, like traditional systems, face cybersecurity threats, handling large volumes of sensitive data. Breaches can lead to severe consequences, requiring substantial investment for strong security and privacy controls. These platforms must

implement measures for data privacy, integrity, breach prevention, identity, authentication, and secure data transfer. Adhering to regulatory compliance, including data protection laws, is crucial. However, maintaining security and privacy is more challenging in these platforms compared to traditional systems given following considerations: **Data sharing complexity** in the European Data Ecosystem involves exchanging data among multiple parties, raising the risk of exposure, unauthorized access, and breaches during transmission. **Trust and anonymity** concerns in data marketplaces necessitate a delicate balance to encourage stakeholder participation. The trade of personal data, especially when individuals act as providers and large entities as buyers, can unintentionally disclose personal information, creating an imbalance.

For future research endeavors, it is imperative to develop comprehensive and dynamic strategies that consistently uphold data security. For future research endeavors, it is imperative to develop comprehensive and dynamic strategies that consistently uphold data security in whole phases of the data marketplace development process including: First, elicitation and specification of security and privacy requirements. This process requires the early involvement of the stakeholders of the data marketplaces in question. Second, designing secure architecture by exploring structural and behavior patterns that embed security measures, like GDPR-compliant data handling mechanisms, encryption, and privacy-preserving techniques. Third, continuous validation and verification. Data protection standards in Europe are evolving rapidly [13]. Therefore, continuous verification to ensure security compliance is a must requirement.

- (2) *Ensuring Transparency*. Ensuring transparency is a mandatory requirement in data ecosystems. For example, to make an informed decision, the data provider requires the availability of a transparent process to understand the implemented criteria and procedures by the broker for data valuation. The absence of clear communication channels creates uncertainty about the fairness and legitimacy of transactions. To address this issue data marketplaces should develop and implement standardized strategies for data valuation. In the case of AI-based data valuation, data marketplaces should implement explainable algorithms to enhance trust by providing explanations for valuation decisions. However, European data platforms involve interaction between different stakeholders with different backgrounds. This issue makes it difficult to offer one comprehensive strategy to ensure transparency between all involved stakeholders.
- (3) *Assessing Data quality*. Assessing Data Quality. Adhering to FAIR principles [14] and ensuring data quality such as data accuracy, and completeness is crucial for data ecosystems. For example, data buyers require access to tools and techniques to measure data quality before purchase. For this, European data ecosystems should provide transparent metadata systems and standardized data-quality assessment tools for enhancing trust and transparency.
- (4) *Ensuring Scalability*. Ensuring Scalability. Due to the many data transactions, scalability represents a main challenge in European data platforms. Addressing this issue requires significant investments in infrastructure for distributed processing and analysis. Research avenues in federate data processing and blockchain can enhance

transaction speeds and data integrity. Moreover, edge and fog computing solutions represent another opportunity to improve efficiency and scalability.

- (5) *Ensuring Data Interoperability*. The mutual understanding of the shared data is a cornerstone for effective data exchange. However, achieving semantic interoperability understanding is often a challenge depending on the data the clarity and accuracy of the vocabulary, and the metadata provided to describe the data. The recent advancements in machine learning, especially Large Language Models, show promising direction for addressing this challenge and enhancing the data exchange.
- (6) *Data ownership and Intellectual Property and Governance*. Complexities in understanding data ownership and intellectual property pose a general challenge in the data ecosystem. Violating such rights will lead to legal consequences. Therefore, engineers should develop robust methodologies with clear policies and processes for accessing, processing, and sharing data to ensure compliance and responsible usage of that data.

7 Conclusions

The data ecosystem is evolving rapidly and this development is not out of challenges but at the same time provides great opportunities for data monetization. Our findings show that organizations must invest in data platforms that demonstrate compliance with data security and privacy regulations while supporting quality-related aspects such as scalability and flexibility. We believe that real-time data analytics and customer-centric approaches will be key differentiators between different organizations and companies in the competitive market.

The analyses in the domain of the ecosystem reveal a resilient IT infrastructure. The scenarios presented provide insight on potential trajectories, emphasizing the robustness of data-related sector. The categorization of stakeholders and detailed insights into technology implementation underscore the multifaceted nature of data monetization. The identified current needs act as a strategic guide for organizations seeking to capitalize on data opportunities. Overall, the analysis paints a comprehensive picture of the European data ecosystem, offering valuable insights for stakeholders and businesses aiming to navigate and thrive in the evolving data-driven paradigm.

Acknowledgments. This research was partially supported by the EU's Horizon Digital, Industry, and Space program under grant agreement ID 101092989-DATAMITE. Also, we thanks to Science Foundation Ireland Grant No. 12/RC/2289 for funding the Insight Centre of Data Analytics.

Disclosure of Interests. No competing interests.

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